

Gesture, Act, Consciousness. The Social Interpretation of the Self in George Herbert Mead

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1. The pragmatist context and James's radical empiricism

As Morris writes in his introduction to *Mind, Self and Society*, the principal merit of pragmatism was to offer a view of mind and intelligence able to take into account both evolutionism and the core ideas of American political revolution. "This doctrine has dramatically called attention to the factor of developmental change in the world (...). The implication seemed to be that not only the human organism but the entire life of mind as well had to be interpreted within the evolutionary development" (Mead, 1934: IX). We can interpret in this light the radical criticism that pragmatism gives to the notion of consciousness (as related to the atomic conception of the individual) and to ontological dualism (as connected to mechanism and the unequal division of the society).

In the years between the 19th and 20th centuries, we witness many attempts of

weakening the eternal opposition between mind and matter, the physical and psychical worlds. In the US, William James – following some intuitions by Charles Sanders Peirce, co-founder of the pragmatist movement – was surely the one who put the final word on the division between the psychical field of mental phenomena and the physical field of natural data. On this ground, he was led to devalue, with very good arguments, "the non-entity called consciousness" (James, 1912: 2), and to provide an image of reality where the *experience* of the world and the *experiential activity* replaced respectively the idea of a transcendental consciousness and the mere factuality of the given. As for James, it was necessary to conceive the world as the "simultaneous" apparition of a same matter or "stuff", that we only represent either *as* physical or *as* mental, but which is neither physical nor mental (on the metaphysical plane). Therefore, he finally talks of "radical empiricism", by substituting the famous expression "stream of consciousness", developed in the *Principles of Psychology*, with the idea of a continuous stream of experience. In one of his last conferences, James expressed himself in a wholly inquisitive manner with respect to the existence of consciousness, and finally understands it in purely functional and non-substantial terms. He claimed that the spiritual principle of man had become a purely ghostly entity in the hands of such writers as Schuppe, Natorp, Munsterberg. "I believe – he wrote – that consciousness when once it

has evaporated to this estate of pure diaphaneity, is on the point of disappearing altogether". It is "a mere echo, the faint rumor left behind by the disappearing soul upon the air of philosophy" (James, 1912: 3). In order to avoid this outcome, we have to adhere to the vision of a "radical experience": an immanent *that* which shows itself so as it is, before the intentionality of consciousness and before the appearance of a given 'out there', before any qualified *what*. Thus, the act of knowing is always the "addition" of a specific determination that produces a detachment from the field of radical experience. In other words, to know is an activity, not so different from many others, and not at all a foundational one. Let's then substitute the distinction between consciousness and world with "that of an absolute experience not due to two factors", but spread in a pragmatic equivalent. "My thesis is that if we start with the supposition that there is only one primal stuff or material in the world, a stuff of which everything is composed, and if we call that stuff 'pure experience', the knowing can easily be explained as a particular sort of relation towards one another into which portions of experience may enter" (James, 1912: 7). Things and thoughts are not "heterogenous", but are made of the same matter that cannot be *defined*, but can just be *experienced*. This is the "matter of experience". Mead wrote that "there has been of late in philosophy a growing recognition of the importance of James's insistence that a great deal has

been placed in consciousness that must be returned to the so-called objective world" (Mead, 1934: 4).

James referred to consciousness as an *addition* to the field of experience. However, consciousness has been traditionally found, at least in Western thought, by *epoché*, reduction, precision, abstraction or, in a single word, *subtraction*. According to the Western framework, then, consciousness, with its rational states and faculties, would appear at the end of a process of philosophical purification of the empirical ground. From Brentano's intentionality to Husserl's transcendental consciousness, from Sartre's imaginative and essentially free consciousness to the call of consciousness and the choice of authenticity that inspired Heidegger's *Sein und Zeit* (and his Agostinian temper), most of Western 20th century philosophy is 'consciousness-oriented'. For this reason, the alternative path followed by James and Mead (and we should certainly add Peirce)¹ has been obscured by the dominant Cartesian framework. The aim of this article is to point out the relevance of these American masters and to survey the consequences of their thoughts in respect to a profound revision of the phenomenology of consciousness and of rationality.

¹ Peirce as worked on the 'destruction' of introspection and the leading role of consciousness as much as James. See on this point "Some Consequences of Four Incapacities", in Peirce (1992: 28-55).

James's pragmatism was taken on by George Herbert Mead² at the beginning of 20th century. Mead developed his mentor's thought by contributing to the field of social psychology and working on a reconsideration of the concepts of Self, gesture, and language. We owe to him a complete reconfiguration, in genealogical terms, of mind and consciousness: "If we abandon the conception of a substantive soul endowed with the self of the individual at birth, then we may regard the development of the individual's self, and of his self-consciousness within the field of his experience, as the social psychologist's special interest" (Mead, 1934: 1). This point is

²Some preliminary biographical hints on Mead are needed, given that he is a relatively unknown author, except among social psychologists. Between 1891 and 1931, year of his untimely death, Mead worked almost always at the Chicago University. There, together with Dewey, Mead set up a famous school inspired to the principles of Pragmatism and social psychology. Actively committed even in civil and political society, Mead wrote just a few articles on specialized journals, without ever publishing a monographic essay. His most interesting production has been posthumously collected by his pupils: *Mind, Self and Society* (Mead 1934), a transcription of his most relevant academic lectures; *The Philosophy of the Present* (Open Court, Chicago, 1932); *Philosophy of the Act* (University of Chicago Press, 1938), an important as much as neglected book. In the philosophical field, Mead is scarcely studied. An evaluation of Mead as a philosopher has been provided by Joas (1997). The most important studies on Mead in Italian are Nieddu (1978), Sini (1996), Calcaterra (2008), and Baggio (2015).

actually at stake in an antidualistic and processual vision of the natural world.

Mead's studies were conducted under the direction of Royce (in the light of an idealism focused on semiotic-social themes) and under the influence of Wundt. However, Mead felt that Wundt's approach did not devote enough attention to the social dimension of the act, and he developed a non-reductionist theory of the mind in which the symbolic dimension and the notion of gesture play a crucial role. In Morris's words: "Mead's endeavor is to show that mind and the self are without residue social emergent; and that language, in the form of the vocal gesture, provides the mechanism for their emergence" (Mead, 1934: XIV). These ideas should also be considered the theoretical grounds of social psychology (which has been funded by Mead). They imply a complete rebuilding, based on the hypothesis of evolutionism, of the epistemological architecture that characterizes the Cartesian and modern era. More than a simple disciplinary novelty, Mead's thought amounts to a theoretical revolution, in the way in which the relationship between individual and society, gesture and rationality, psychical and physical world is conceived. Mead interprets the individual psyche as an adaptive result of a founding sociality, and sees sociality not as a mere aggregation of many discrete individuals, but as a result of an act able to test the different degrees of experience. "(...) minds and selves are essentially social products, products or phe-

nomena of the social side of human experience (...)” (Mead, 1934: 2).

By synthesizing the pragmatist and the ‘genealogical’ (by referring to Nietzsche along with Darwin) approaches, Mead proposes a revolutionary view of consciousness that had a strong impact on both psychology and philosophy, as I shall show in what follows.

2. The influence of Darwin and Wundt on Mead’s work

Since the early years of his lecturing activity, George Herbert Mead firmly believes that the theme is to be set up in the following way: consciousness is today attested in the human species, but the problem is how to explain the evolutionary “jump” which has brought to the genesis of such an important and species-related organ. As it might be understood, Mead takes on a position which distances him, on the one hand, from William James, who, as we have seen, had already given farewell years before to that “entity named consciousness”, on the other from a second thinker like-minded with him, John Watson, who used to reduce consciousness, in a behaviorist manner, to the ways of visible conduct.

With respect to the former, Mead’s position is discordant. Despite showing appreciation for his psychological writings, the theory of radical empiricism seems to him to pulverize an ineludible issue: con-

sciousness, with its equipment of expressions and meaningful forms, is actually an indubitable and precious acquisition in the constitution of the human. Still, Mead admits, this is not a matter of fact: consciousness is a symbolic formation which is the outcome of a process of becoming and, throughout evolution, has undergone radical transformations which have turned it into something extremely different from that original sketch of knowledge which it used to be. Even more, contrary to what James used to believe, it is an entirely linguistic phenomenon, which means to all intents and purposes a social phenomenon, and it is not the expression of inward motions. We must then make an effort to trace its genealogy back – a point that James never showed to consider.

With respect to Watson, as Mead points out, “Social psychology is behavioristic in the sense of starting off with an observable activity (...) but it is not behavioristic in the sense of ignoring the inner experience of the individual – the inner phase of that process or activity. On the contrary, it is particularly concerned with the rise of such an experience within the process as a whole. It simply works from the outside to the inside” (Mead, 1934: 7-8). Consciousness is mostly to be explained, not to be certified; what must be explained is its development, its function, its usefulness. It clarifies itself as emergency, initially scarcely relevant. What does allow it to advance and impose itself?

As we can see, Mead thinks in a Darwinian fashion – consciousness is an evolutionary effect – and behavioristically – consciousness makes its first appearance as a form of conduct visible in its sensible effects – still he does not miss the opportunity to take account of the lesson of the idealists, with whom he was acquainted thanks to Royce. His view might be well defined as a phenomenology of consciousness, genealogically and symbolically oriented. “We want to approach language not from the standpoint of inner meanings to be expressed, but in its larger context of cooperation in the group taking places by means of signals and gestures. Meaning appears within that process. Our behaviorism is a social behaviorism” (Mead, 1934: 6). Mead’s starting point is based on some of Wundt’s best insights. The German psychologist had underlined the dynamical structure of consciousness and had proposed a parallelism between psychical and physiological events. With some affinities with the work that James (with Lange) was doing in the field of the theory of emotions (cfr. Mead, 1934: 20-1), Wundt found a parallelism between the phenomena of consciousness and the physical mechanisms in the body. And these operations are “located inside of the act, for all takes place in the body is action” (Mead, 1934: 21). Nothing can be solely a static, physiological and mechanical state. “We come to the sensations and undertake to state them in terms of complete reflex action. We deal with the sensation from the standpoint of the stimu-

lus, and when we come to deal with the various emotional states we deal with them in terms of the preparation for action and the act itself as it is going on”. The different sets of psychical acts are nothing but the different phases of the act. “Parallelism, then, is an attempt to find analogues between action and experienced contents” (Mead, 1934: 21). In Mead’s radical interpretation of these parts of Wundt’s theory, consciousness has to be seen essentially “from the point of view of action” (Mead, 1934: 22) “with an emphasis upon conduct, upon the dynamic rather than the static” (Mead, 1934: 24). We cannot observe *states* of consciousness, but just *acts* of conscience, as pure dispositions to behave. These dispositions cannot be found, however, in a central nervous system, because its unity is just a “unity of integration” (Mead, 1934: 24). In conclusion, Mead notes the ambiguity of the term ‘consciousness’: it cannot be used to build some form of parallelism with physiology, and it seems to need itself an explanation and a genealogy. The proper object of psychology will not be, therefore, consciousness, but the experience of the individual in its relation to the conditions under which experience expands itself. “What I am insisting upon is that the patterns which one finds in the central nervous system are patterns of action – not of contemplation.” (Mead, 1934: 26).

Human agents have a readiness to act or general disposition toward the objects of the world, which is made possible by a cer-

tain organization of the nervous system that grounds certain possibilities of action. For example, a distant object is always spatially approached in the light of the practical purpose that will be realized when the contact with the object will become possible. The later stages of the act are already present in the early stages, and they determine how we are going to approach the object and the steps in our manipulation of it.³ We might start from here in order to explain every anthropological form of structuring: the first step is the act, which is not for the most part willed, intentioned, decided, but which is simply performed. The crucial datum in psychology, as Mead notices (Mead, 1934: 8), is the act, not the individual tract, and the act is an ‘organic’ and socially rooted process. It is never exerted singularly, but demands a shared and publicly recognized practice.

Mead keeps, then, some important acquisitions of Wundt, and mostly the following one: each and every behavior stems from a gesture, which is to be considered as the nucleus out of which the act spreads. The gesture, then, is initially the simple incentive that triggers a social response⁴. It is the gesture that enables the reciprocal adjustments between different individual organisms, which provokes an appropriate

³ It is worth noting the assonance between these parts of Mead’s theory and the actual researches on “cognition in action” and “affordances”.

⁴ The gestures are “early stages of social acts that precede the symbol proper, and deliberate communication” (Mead, 1934: 15).

response, within which any organism performs its own part so contributing to the constitution of the act in its wholeness and by producing a behavioral analogy.

Mead’s stance is less Darwinist than it might seem at a face value: in fact, in *The Expression of the Emotions in Man and Animals*, Darwin wisely analyzed the gestures leading to the expression of the emotional attitude of individuals, but, as a matter of fact, he hypothesized the shift from an inner (mental) state to an exterior (expressive) state, position which does not convince Mead (Darwin, 1872). There is no evidence, as he thinks, to postulate the existence of states of consciousness vibrating beyond and before the expressive gestures. The same objection is addressed to his master Wundt, and just in relation to the concept, among other things enlightening, of “gesture”. No gesture is given as exteriorization of a process of thought: simply, the act is the whole and it is also the *primum* from which one must start. Wundt recognized very well that the primitive situation is that of the social act which involves the interaction of different forms, and the reciprocal adjustment of the conduct of these forms. However, he did not realize that these different phases of the act do not always carry with them what we call an “inner attitude” (Mead, 1934: 45). “If we assume that there is a certain psychical state answering to a physical state how are we going to get to the point where the gesture will arouse the *same* gesture in the attitude of the other individual? In the very begin-

ning the other person's gesture means what you are going to do about it" (Mead, 1934: 49). The last point is worth stressing. The gesture, in its primitive stages, is not a sign of an emotion or of an idea: it is simply a signal that asks for a response. According to Mead, Wundt, in fact presupposes the Self as an antecedent to the social processes in order to explain communication, whereas the Self must be accounted for in terms of the social process. By presupposing the existence of the mind right from the start, Wundt fails to give an explanation of its arising in the process of communication. "Then the origin of minds and the interaction among minds remain mysteries" (Mead, 1934: 50). Finally, Wundt overlooks the importance of communication in the origin of what we call 'mind'; his parallelism remains a dualism.

3. A conversation of gestures

Let us carefully consider Mead's position: according to him, gestures are responses, not reflections, as he says. Thus, they are actions, which are empirically observable and pragmatically assessable. These actions are repeatable and, in the long run, they become habitual. Therefore, they become various and gradually more complex forms of life. The centrality of the act – and in the first place of the gestural act – is a theoretical move which, in itself, ratifies the philosophical relevance of Mead, and that definitely dis-

tinguishes him from most of the social psychologists whose ideas were influential at that time, and who also worked in Chicago.

If read under a philosophical perspective, his path brings us to say, along with Carlo Sini⁵, that the gesture works as a true world-openness, inasmuch as it inscribes a primeval nucleus of *in fieri* praxis, in-cising the real and de-ciding the course (*poros*) of experience⁶. The gesture is an emergence which changes the surrounding horizon, by tracing in it the furrow of a path. It is the pragmatic unity *par excellence*: a "grapheme", a writing of the body and, all together, of the world⁷ – or, better, the birthplace of both these polarities. "The gesture is not 'someone's gesture'; on the contrary, each and everyone is entrusted to the event of the gesture" (Sini, 1996, 21). In its opening itself up, the gesture calls for an answer: it lays out the harmonic threshold of the responding and of the cor-responding, thus allowing the concordance, the shared resounding of the living beings.

⁵ In my reading of this topic I particularly follow Sini (1996).

⁶ 'Experience' stems from the Latin words *ex-perior*, meaning "finding a way which leads out of". Within the theme survives the Greek word *poros*, which stands for "path", "itinerary", "stratagem".

⁷ "The gesture is the happening of that border, of that threshold, so that there is something to do, that is, there is something to respond and correspond to what happens" (Sini, 1996: 20).

Mead's favorite example is that of the dog fighting, which he designates as a "conversation between gestures". A dog sets out to attack the rival dog: to hypothesize the existence of an inner canine consciousness to which the exterior gesture of the teeth-grinding corresponds is nothing but an anthropomorphic projection of the state which we have learnt to determine as 'conscious'. Gestures here are not "meaningful" yet; a dog does not reflect over what is going to happen and does not decide to shift itself because it is aware of the consequences of its and other people's behavior.

Notably, what offers itself to our view is only the reciprocal adjustment of stimuli and responses, of actions and reactions which, in this case, are dissimilar. To the first dog's stimulus of rage responds the reaction of fear of the second: a dog launches an attack, the other flees away. Like in a dance, positions change in a reciprocal connection with the partner's movement, they adapt themselves to the change of his gestures. There is no language here, no intention or psychism is attestable. "The other person's gesture means what you are going to do about it. It does not mean what he is thinking about or even his emotion" (Mead, 1934: 49). The first gesture means the performed action of the attack, the second the unavoidable reaction of the escape. The symbol has not arisen yet, because there is no sharing of common attitudes. The same thing happens – although with a stronger reciprocity – when we si-

lently answer to a glance launched in the air just in our direction: enticed into a "common place", we find ourselves somehow compelled to respond, that is, to take part in the act, as if a ball had been thrown at us which we find instinctive to prevent from falling down. We swiftly tune in the gestural openness of the other- even if only by lowering our eyes – and it is just this mutual correspondence that determines the subsequent relation, with its symbolic and mediated practice.

Mead analyzes with phenomenological subtlety these steps of progressive reciprocal adjustment and starts thinking that consciousness comes 'ex post', so to speak, that it raises up as an *outcome* of these adjustments, as a specialization designed to achieve a better concordance. Gestures do not presuppose consciousness. Rather, consciousness is the product of the acts becoming more and more complex and reciprocal.

He follows the example - an extremely convincing one – of the relation between the parent form and the kid form: the succession between the "stimulating cry, the answering tone on the part of the parent-form and the consequent change in the cry of the child-form" (Mead, 1934: 44) become stimuli for a reciprocal re-adaptation until the social act gets accomplished in the most satisfactory way for both, thanks to a *syn-
tony* which is not simply the intermingling and synthesizing of the voices. So the child has his own self in that 'other' from himself which is the breast: the thing for which he

experiences his being 'breast-fed'. But even the mother has her own self into the other who is the child, for whom she is mother and source of nourishment. The gesture of the cry of the breast-fed is a stimulus which calls for caring, activating a series of answers more and more elaborate which will bring to language and to the reciprocal understanding, thanks to the activation of a shared meaning. On this side, I think that the considerations by the great infant psychologist Daniel Stern (1985) could be useful, too. According to him, the resonance between mother and child is produced exactly following the rhythm of a continuous connection performed at the right attunement of the daily care practices. An infinite number of times will the mother propose "themes" in her games with the newborn and an infinite number of times will the child vary them with his crossed glances, lallations and cries. Knowledge will be produced in the syn-phony between a glance and a gesture, a gesture and a movement, a movement and a vocal reply. It is not really here a matter of imitation but of an "affect contagion", writes Stern, of a gestural pragmatics, exactly as a conversation of gestures, in Mead's sense, which has not that much to do with the cognitive involvement.

The act is then the outright 'fact'; a fact straightforwardly social and not surely elementary, that paves the way for the setting up of subjectivity and interiority. Original is the communicative conduct, the 'for' of the reference towards something

other in taking distance 'from' other; the hendiadys of co-science⁸. The intentionality and cogitating rationality supervene at a second time:

Contrary to Darwin, however, we find no evidence for the prior existence of consciousness as something which brings about behavior on the part of one organism that is of such a sort as to call forth an adjustive response on the part of another organism, without itself being dependent on such behavior. We are rather forced to conclude that consciousness is an emergent from such behavior; that so far from being a precondition of the social act, the social act is a precondition of it. The mechanism of the social act can be traced out without introducing into it the conception of consciousness as a separable element within that act; hence the social act, in its more elementary stages or forms, it is possible without, or apart from, some form of consciousness. (Mead, 1934: 17-18)

Organism and environment, then, are always involved in a pragmatic-gestural relation which marks the creation of a perspective on the world, an articulation in pre-semiotic terms, but certainly already anticipatory of symbols. As Mead in fact writes, the shift from the gesture to the symbol in human culture occurs rapidly. When gestures become the vehicles of an intentional and aware communication, fundamentally institutionalized, the symbolic apparatus with its supply of meanings makes its appearance. But the specific nature of symbolic experience, as we'll see

⁸ We must not forget that the etymological root of the word is *cum-scientia* or, as Tertullian used to put it, *communis complurium scientia*.

immediately, is not conventional, and lies properly in that process which Mead defines as *taking the attitudes of the others* or *taking the role of the other*.

4. Taking the role of the other

Let us see how this further passage in the genealogy of conscience configures itself. When the gesture expresses an idea which presupposes it, and, at the same time, the same idea emerges in another subject, then we enter the field of an outright symbolic exchange. When the gesture evokes in us the same response and the same attitude which the gesture evokes in the others (the rage itself of the first dog, as it were, and not a reaction of escape and fear), here we have a symbolic conversation and no longer a purely gestural one. It is evident, then, that in the animal world such an exchange gives itself in rare and specific cases. It is in the anthropologic environment, precisely in the place where language and signification do arise, that such a process sets itself up in the fullest way: in fact, it is the only one which entails a symbol that has a meaning for the first individual, who, in turn, evokes the same meaning in the second individual, who is now recognized by the social group. The meaningful gesture, then, makes the subject who accomplishes it aware of the others' attitude towards the gesture itself, and allows him to adjust his own behavior subsequent to that of other

individuals in compliance with that given attitude. The answer to the first gesture started up by me gets then "impersonated" and assimilated by others: I take on myself such a new attitude by rebound, playing from within the relation the same role as the one who is in front of me, a role which allows me to recognize myself, making the gesture of the other become part of my being conscious of the whole situation. In order to structure my own interiority, I am compelled to *alter* and *communicate myself*: only in other people's response, broadly and generically speaking, I retrieve the boundaries of my own self and of its (very important for life in society) states of consciousness. Consciences – we might say – stem from a process of disambiguation with respect to an originally blurred and promiscuous ground of continuous exchange between the involved parts.

In order to better comment on his proposal (which is in fact only vaguely foreshadowed in his writings, so that one must work hard to tease out of it the philosophical reminder), let us make a simple example. In this first communicational relationship, as we have noted, the stimulating gesture is different from the responding one and we are spectators of pure idiosyncratic conducts, although reciprocally accommodated and belonging to a common act. To the child's cry the parent's care follows, but only for the one who observes and is equipped with conceptual tools linked to the concept of causality and responsibility. It is not certainly so for the

child, and, only in a confuse manner, for the new parent. Still, step by step, the adult and the newly born baby will tune themselves to a shared response, which will establish for anyone that one cries *in order to* be looked after. It is here that sign and signification do make their appearance. However, in order to effectively promote a shift from a conversation between gestures to a symbolic conversation, along with the upsurge of that fundamental gesture which is the vocal one, a different condition must be given. It is not sufficient for the stimulus A to ‘provoke’ (that is, literally speaking, to call for) the response B. It must even stimulate itself to give the same answer as B, which, then, will no longer become ‘mine’ or ‘your’ own response, but a response commonly negotiated and publicly participated; that is, an answer which is no longer mine or yours, but – generically and much more efficaciously – ours. In order to do that, I take the attitude of the other, I ‘evoke’ (etymologically: call from the outside) in myself the same answer which I evoke in other people, I answer *as if* I were the other, or, even better, as if I were all the other participants in the linguistic ‘game’. I assume, then, a common idea behind the conduct (mother and son both think of the pap), that is, I hypothesize a consciousness which acts as a coordinating agent of the organized responses. The invention of consciousness is substantially designed to the following aim: to persuade oneself of one’s being part of a common world, to communicate himself to

others. Even for Mead consciousness is first and foremost *communis complurium scientia*.

We are more or less unconsciously seeing ourselves as others see us. We are unconsciously addressing ourselves as others address us; in the same way as the sparrow takes up the note of the canary we pick up the dialects about us. (...) We are calling out in the other person something we are calling out in ourselves, so that unconsciously we take over these attitudes. We are unconsciously putting ourselves in the place of others and acting as others act. I want simply to isolate the general mechanism here, because it is of very fundamental importance in the development of what we call self-consciousness and the appearance of the self. We are, especially through the use of vocal gestures, continually arousing in ourselves those responses which we call out in other persons, so that we are taking the attitudes of the other persons into our own conduct (Mead, 1934: 68-9).

The “internalization” of conversation of gestures which we carry on with other individuals, Mead concludes, fully and legitimately constitutes the essence of thinking (Mead, 1934: 47); and ‘mentalization’, as it is generally said today, implies taking other people’s acts as if they were one’s own, in a rebound from the explicit being observable from the outside to the implicit which is internally stated. Thus, internalization means, just as it used to be for Nietzsche, a counter-stroke in virtue of which the self lifts up and imposes itself starting from the ‘average measure’ established by common thinking. Consciousness, as we read in the *Gay Science*, does not belong to the individual, but to the “social and communitarian side” (Nietz-

sche, 2001: § 354) and man only is the “sign-inventing man” who can afford it.

Mead thinks exactly in the same way as Nietzsche (in whose view, however, the common is not certainly the gregarious, nor is it what conduces man to get sick): we interiorize the primitive conversation of gestures and assimilate the public and conventional answers, by making them become private and by depositing them in a shared place which we define as ‘mind’ or ‘consciousness’. But the ‘my’ remains what originally it used to be: the ‘ours’, or, better said, the ‘other’s’, taken on as “mirror” and “surface” of consciousness. As in the germinal forms of reflections typical of Archaic Greece, the Self addresses the “I” in the second person and only in this way it manages to detect it and tease it out from the circularity of the acts. “And hence the origin and foundations of the self, like those of thinking, are social” (Mead, 1934: 173). With reference to this, I will confine myself to quoting once again one passage of *Mind, Self and Society*, among the many dedicated to a lucid outline of the issue: “Selves must be accounted for in terms of the social process, and in terms of communication; and individuals must be brought into essential relation within that process before communication, or the contact between the minds of different individuals, become possible” (Mead, 1934: 49-50). What comes first is this essential “ontology of relation”. The same body does not originally experience itself as belonging to a self: it becomes as such when it “de-

velops a mind in the context of social experience” (Mead, 1934: 49-50). This is an extremely simple and appropriate definition of an ancient and long-debated issue: only when it emerges something which is defined as “mind”, thanks to the symbolic exchange operated within that bigger body which is the society, we can say that we have a body and that body and mind constitute our own self⁹. As Mead puts it: “Mind arises through communication by a conversation of gestures in a social process or context of experience – not communication through mind” (Mead, 1934: 50). Thus, we can finally say that “language as made up of significant symbols is what we mean by mind” (Mead, 1934: 190 n.18).

In the second, symbolic phase of the social encounter we envisage not only the cor-respondence, as it happens in the conversation between gestures, but the projection, the analogy of conduct, the replacement of the self with the other and that of the other with the self and, therefore, the outright constitution of one’s own personality thanks to the activation of the highly

⁹ Continues Mead: “For if, as Wundt does, you presuppose the existence of mind at the start, as explaining or making possible the social process of experience, than the origin of minds and the interactions among minds become mysteries. But if, on the other hand, you regard the social process of experience as prior (in a rudimentary form) to the existence of mind and explain the origin of minds in terms of the interaction among individuals within that process, than not only the origin of minds, but also the interactions among minds cease to be mysterious or miraculous” (*ibidem*).

symbolic mechanism of the *as if*: ultimately, a metaphor-generating activity which allows me to transfer myself (*meta-pherein*) in the role of the other. Which means: to take on the *mask* of the other and only in this way to become ‘*person*’¹⁰.

I recognize my inwardness in the exteriority of the other’s gesture, I transfer (*meta-phero*) the “outside” into the “inside”. That I have a “Me” is therefore a counter-stroke of the intention which I attach to you in the process of formulation of a symbolic act, by conceiving of it as *similar* to the one which leads myself to express the way I do. *Taking the role of the others* is to be understood as “playing with masks” with others, ‘wearing the mask of the community’¹¹. At the very origin we do not find pure thought, nor functioning consciousness, but communication, conversation, role-exchange¹², *theater* plays. Consciousness – as Royce already used to indicate it - is a crowded place, a noisy one, unfit for a meditative introspection (Fabbrichesi, 2012; Miller, 1975). Mead mean-

¹⁰ As it is well known, the Latin word ‘person’ meant ‘mask’. See on that topic Cicero’s *De officiis*, where it is made clear how each person is to wear a mask which suits one’s own private or public role well, and, even better, which suits the many different social roles one is called to perform. Personality is therefore with no doubt multifaceted, and whoever performs an institutional role is called to wear the mask of the city, that is, of the community, in its wholeness.

¹¹ See above, footnote 10.

¹² The same thought is to be considered as “implicit conversation with oneself” (Mead, 1934: 90).

ingly insists on this point: consciousness is a *theatrical* scene.

Until this process has been developed into the abstract process of thought, self-consciousness remains *dramatic*, and the self which is a fusion of the remembered actor and this accompanying chorus is somewhat loosely organized and very clearly social. Later the inner stage changes into the forum and workshop of thought. The features and intonations of the *dramatis personae* fade out and the emphasis falls upon the meaning of the inner speech, the imagery becomes merely the barely necessary cues. But the mechanism remains social, and at any moment the process may become personal. (Mead, 1913: 2)

5. The vocal gesture

Among many symbolic acts, the most emblematic of all, as the true founder of self-consciousness, is the vocal gesture. Mead has devoted extraordinary pages to set out such a concept. The voice (or the scream – for instance, the first scream of the child) comes from the ‘outside’, even for whoever emits it. There is an anonymous and impersonal ‘It screams’, which bounces back both to who addresses and to who is addressed, by situating simultaneously their answers. The voice explodes in any direction, literally gashing the world, by causing a sense to resonate. The voice comes for everybody: not only for me who scream and amaze myself at my screaming, not only for you who are listening, but for each of us, in a very well-spread out field of the audible. It evokes in me the same answer

that it evokes in the other, especially when it becomes meaningful and awakens a common idea correlated to it. In the development of such “con-science” [*co-scire*], I can fix *as a consequence* the limits of my personal *scire* and understand the role which I perform in the “it screams”. The voice comes first and foremost for me, for the ‘me’ who I am. It is the voice that objectivates me as a speaking and, therefore, thinking subject. The self is so the outcome and the origin of the voice, the origin inasmuch as it is the outcome, spring and, all the same, effect of the imperious vocalism of communicating oneself. The vocal gesture fixes the Mine and the Other people’s, subjectivity and inter-subjectivity, and it is only stemming from the gestural explosion of vocalism that the two poles dispose themselves within the circle of the responding and the cor-responding. The vocal gesture, then, presents a special reflexivity of its own, by realizing an “auto-affective” and “auto-graphic” capacity which no other sign succeeds in reaching¹³.

There is a specific “enchantment of vocal gestures” (Mead, 1934: 102), i.e. one that persists even when the child learns how to undertake a dialogue with the others. An enchantment which in every cul-

¹³ On these topics, besides the already mentioned Sini, see for a phenomenological analysis also Di Martino (2005) and Bourgeois (1990). It is worth noting that Derrida (2003), provided an analysis of the phenomenon of the voice not so different than Mead’s – but by making no reference at all to the latter.

ture subsequently turns into the wisdom and melodic articulation of the singing in its proper form. Whereof there was peace, thereof there is a scream which tears the silence, which says something *about me to me* and the others, which imposes me and the others to myself. The vocal gesture does never have characters of privacy: just as the conscience which it brings about, it is an eminently public phenomenon. Eventually, the meaningful vocal gesture, just insofar as it does not possess specific objects differently from touch or taste, has them somehow at its own disposal. The voice is the only sensory organ which produces new things, literally, un-heard of. Its poverty is its richness: it gives a name to something that cannot be found, that is the universal point of view, the public truth – in other words: the concept (Sini, 1996: 35). Of course, that includes the concept of “I”.

The universality and publicity of the reference implied by the vocal signs fix the latter properly symbolical element and the presupposition of ‘reality’. For that reason, as we might say, when between two persons a shift takes place from conversation between gestures, as glances for instance might be, to word-exchange, one is compromised and an outright affective relationship – whether good or bad - gets undertaken. Unlike any other gesture, the word elicits identical meanings in all those who listen, publicly recognized meanings and bearers of universality. By saying ‘table’ we will all head for the table and ‘will be ready to use’ the table in the same way;

by pronouncing the word 'love' we will have defined in a conceptual sense and 'for all' that elusive responding which used to attract us, but that could immediately be dismissed.

How does – Mead wonders – such a community of response structure itself? By pure imitation? It is important for the American psychologist to wonder how language arises, by offering a hypothesis which is not content to speak of imitation, as it has been done to overcome Wundt's difficulties. When we hear the birds' singing and admire the sparrow's warbles repeating those of the canary, it seems to us that they enact an imitative process, such as the one which appears in the baby who learns how to speak from the parents' mot-toes. But it is not really a matter of imitation, as Mead says: it is a strengthening of one's own answer to the other, modeled on the other's vocalism, in the attempt to elicit in oneself the attitude one arises in the others. There is, then, an incorporation of the gesture of the other and an empowerment of its own, by trial and error (as it in fact happens in the infant's lallation, who tries to "tune in" better and better on the verse of the adult). The sparrow uses the same note as the canary not simply by repeating it, but also and especially by responding and evoking in himself the counter alter of the one who flies besides him. In fact, the sparrow responds 'to the point'. In this way, it affects in a double-fold way both himself and the canary in the act of listening. There is no imitation, then,

but the retrieval of an identical attitude to the purpose of accentuating the symbolic reach (Cf. Mead, 1934: 51). We are faced to the structuring of the transcendental condition of language, as emergence from the 'common' basis of the practical responses which intervene in the different forms of life.

6. The Generalized Other and the Social Self

Mead tells us even more about the 'common thought' by introducing a notion which will have a great fortune: that of the *Generalized Other*. Self-consciousness and the Self, as he explains, configure themselves only if expressed in a collective undertaking. But then we have to accept that, in order to become a self or a "social object", it is necessary to identify ourselves with what can be named "the Generalized Other". "The organized community or social group which gives to the individual his unity of self may be called 'Generalized Other'. The attitude of the generalized other is the attitude of the community" (Mead, 1934: 154). It is only by taking the role of the others, and especially by taking the role of that Other that is an organization of the attitudes of those involved in the same process, that we can get back to ourselves. Such *Generalized Other* is the community, that structures the individual in his own organic unity as member of a 'superior' body: every single

individual must take on this aware attitude by adopting well defined rules within the social game, he must learn how to assume this *common* role (that is, neither exclusively mine nor yours, but both mine and yours), and not simply the role of the other who confronts me; he must prove to be able to know how to play the game of his time and of his group. The notion of *game* then becomes fundamental: games are principally mediated by language, they are ‘language games’, as Wittgenstein would have said. Mead considers *game* as something different than mere *play* (Mead, 1934: § 20). In the *game* we see that not only an “alter-a[c]tion”, but a “comuna[c]tion” is produced. The distinction between *play* and *game* guides Mead in these central pages of his work: he analyzes the organized unity of the team-game (a privileged example is baseball), in which I must take part in the match by knowing how to indistinctively assume the roles of the various players and by learning how to take my action under control in conformity to them, by equipping it with normativity. Alternatively, suffice it to think of language, in which we assume the role of all the speakers of a certain *langue*¹⁴, and we learn how to control our expressions, by sticking to some rules. Different are the

things, evidently, in the free play, where the child identifies himself in a role and then in another (I act *as* the fireman, *as* the princess), with no organization, with no hierarchical and architectural units, with no finality.

By gradually identifying himself as the Generalized Other of his own community, and by assuming the attitude of the whole group, the child finally equips himself with a Self, equally Organized and Social. It becomes clear what allows Mead to say that I am “the others” and, particularly, I am the “Other” ‘in general’. “The structure, then, on which the self is built is this response which is common to all. For one has to be a member of a community to be a self” (Mead, 1934: 162). In the ultimate analysis, as Mead writes, self-consciousness means nothing but “an awakening in ourselves of the group of attitudes which are arousing in others, especially when it is an important set of responses which go to make up the members of the community” (Mead, 1934: 163). Any attempt to distinguish the Self from the Others is doomed to defeat, because precisely our selves do exist and come to be part of our experience inasmuch as we experience the selves of the others throughout their attitudes and common living (Calcaterra, 2008). The author concludes in a poetical and impressive way, in one of the few writings come down to us in their published form: “The desire of knowledge of the conditions in which other populations live, work, love or fight springs up from that fundamental curiosity

¹⁴ I refer to the distinction between *langue* and *parole* evoked by De Saussure in his *Cours de linguistique general*, which I will later deal with, as a distinction between competence and execution in the use of a language.

that is the passion of self-consciousness. We must be the others if we want to be ourselves” (Mead, 1924-5: 277).

7. Self, I, Me

Let us now focus on the Self, a topic which Mead deals with in a very important writing, *The Social Self*, published in 1913 and above quoted. According to Mead, the difference between the Self and the physical organism is that the former can see itself as an object.

The English word *self* brings us back to the reflexive which indicates at the same time a subjective and an objective form. Just insofar as the Self can be an object to itself, it qualifies itself as a social and collective experience, and not as a personal and inward one. The Self is not “a more or less isolate and independent element (...) When we reach a self we reach a certain sort of conduct, a certain type of social process which involves the interaction of different individuals” (Mead, 1934: 164-5). That is to say, the Self is constituted by an entirely public stuff, by the material distributed by the lives of the others or, more exactly, of the material of the life in common with others. This appears all the more true if we stick to the pioneering investigations of the Austrian psychologist René Spitz. He was the first to describe the behaviors of those kids who, for some reason, were kept apart - for a long time or forever- from the person who used to take care of them, without manag-

ing to find a valid replacement. The physician visited many orphanages, where these kids were looked after very satisfactorily from a physical point of view, still without caring the relational and affective aspect. Many of these children inexplicably deteriorated, in some cases to the point of death. They displayed behaviors like bemoaning and calls (first month of separation), crying and weight lost (second month), rejection of physical contact, delay in motor development, tendency to get diseases, absence of expressiveness, procumbent position (third month), cessation of the crying and rare screams, lethargic state (after the third month). If within the fifth/sixth month of separation the child had the chance to find his attachment figure or someone who could replace it, these symptoms used to disappear; otherwise a coma could occur, or even death (Spitz, 1965). These investigations confirm Mead’s intuition: the structuring of the Self – even from the point of view of physical survival – is a process by all means social and relational. My own Self is, literally, into the hands and the gazes of the others.

This does not mean that one speaks only through the voice of the community. Mead was always mindful at preserving the space of freedom and individual responsibility. In the distinction to which he comes in the third chapter of *Mind, Self and Society*, by distinguishing between Self, I and Me, Mead in fact manages to successfully reach a further articulation of his own psycho-social analysis. A similar distinction had already

been put forward by James, and resonated in Peirce. But Mead has been for sure the first who dealt exhaustively with that topic, and laid it out with sharper clarity. According to him, the Self is to be conceived of as a split into the 'I' and the 'Me'. The 'Me' represents the organized set of attitudes inherited by the community: it is the conventional, institutional aspect of subjectivity, which I tacitly share with others. The I is instead the excess, the atypical emergence, the irreducible singularity which stands against the Me; it is the unforeseeable discard, the idiosyncratic break whose nature we cannot define beforehand. The individual is not only a member of the community, but reacts to that community and, in the reaction itself, he modifies it: his answer to the "organized attitude" provokes the change, at times radical, of the society, in ways that conduce to the steady reset of the collective environment and of the public forms of life. The 'I' creates the 'Me', but at the same time the former reacts to the latter, or is itself created as a reaction to the latter. Thus, both the I and the Me contain *in nuce* different features of the Self. The Self is, in the ultimate analysis, not an entity with a stable core; it is not a substance, but always a predicate. The Self is, so to speak, "an eddy in the social current and so still a part of the current. It is a process in which the individual is continually adjusting himself in advance to the situation he belongs to, and reacting back on it" (Mead, 1934: 182). To sum up, the Self is the correlation between different communicative signs, understood as a "dynamic pro-

cess" of the experience. It does not have the nature as *unicum* and *fundamentum*. On the contrary, its nature is "double": the Self is both 'I' and 'Me', 'I' and 'Other', 'I' and 'Generalized Other', a subjective and objective pole of conduct.

In all these cases, as Mead sharply notes, I cannot still split myself with such a rapidity that I can fully capture my own self in my 'originality'. At the time in which I see and represent myself, I am already far from the "I" and re-conquered by the "Me". The 'I' is therefore "a historical figure", an effect of memory and recognition; what I was a second ago is the 'I' of the 'Me'. "The I is in certain sense that with which we do identify ourselves. The getting of it into experience constitutes one of the problems of most of our conscious experience; it is not directly given to experience" (Mead, 1934: 174-5). The normal situation is one which involves a reaction of the individual which is socially determined, but to which he brings his own responses as an I. Yet, we cannot exhibit the response while responding.

The 'I' emerges then within the folds of the Self; by the time it gets recognized it is already a "Me"; "The 'I' of this moment is the 'me' of the next moment" (Mead, 1934: 174)¹⁵. And 'Me' is the organized, habitual,

¹⁵ "The I of introspection is the self which enters into social relations with other selves". And moreover: "The mechanism of introspection is therefore given in the social attitude which man necessarily assumes towards himself, and the mechanism of thought, in so far as thought uses symbols which are

conventional set of the common attitudes (*the various individuals “Me”*), just as they get deposited thanks to the system of language and symbols. The “I” names to the contrary the emerging of novelty, the competence in singular execution, the modifications, throughout individual answers, of the community asset. The ‘I’ is responsible for the conduct “in the first person”, the one which escapes and will always escape the “social control” which is expression of the ‘Me’. Something similar was thought by De Saussure when he used to distinguish between *langue* and *parole*.

Within the “I” we find the “Me”, or, even, within the “Me” we find the “I”, on which the ‘Me’ never succeeds in keeping hold. The ‘I’ is the break from the ‘Me’ and of the ‘Me’ from the ‘Self’ (because it is, nevertheless, always the chorus of the ‘Me’ which brings to the solo of the ‘I’). And again: it is the Self, structured in the rebound of the community, which generates the ‘Me’ and the ‘I’. The Self as *it-self*, i.e. as a third person who lives within the first.

8. Conclusions

I would like to conclude by quoting an extremely beautiful sentence from a fragment added in a footnote to the first edition of *Mind, Self and Society* (Mead, 1934: 223, n.25). Mead refers to his own

used in social intercourse, is but an inner conversation” (Mead, 1913: 4).

theory by speaking of “a social theory of mind”: if the mind structures itself in a social way, he writes, “the field or locus of any given individual mind must extend as far as the social activity or apparatus of social relations which constitutes it extends; and hence that field cannot be bounded by the skin of the individual organism to which it belongs”. The reference to the horizontal extension of consciousness, outside the borders of the individual skin and brain, leads us to think of an extended and distributed mind, just as the one of which many cognitivist thinkers (see e.g. Clark, 2008) maintain today, thinkers who, I believe, would have much to learn from Mead.

The point is not that George Herbert Mead simply started a new discipline called social psychology, but that he interpreted the individual and inner psyche in a totally innovative manner. He made two very important points, which deserve a more thorough appreciation and interpretation. First, he traced a genealogy of consciousness, by explaining that it is not a datum, an origin, or a principle, but a consequence, a result of the evolution of gestures and symbolic attitudes; second, he explained that consciousness produces itself as a sort of “transfer” from the outside to the inside, from the communal to the individual, and that this transfer is made possible by the use of language and signs. The human being becomes an ‘I’ when he learns how to use the public signs in a private way, when he learns to address himself as others ad-

dress him. The Russian psychologist Vygotsky (1962) can be associated to Mead in this respect. Along the same lines, and more or less in the same years, Vygotsky identified 'external' with 'social' and presumed that consciousness and all the superior functions of the psyche are an outcome of trans-individual social relations. It is exactly the public context and the social recognition that transform a mere impulse into a gesture and a gesture into a symbolic sign, which belong to their users only in a derivative sense. The "internalization" is a cultural operation, made possible by our multiple social and 'external' relations (languages, habits, praxes, rituals, etc.), and all the superior functions of the psyche constituting the personality are born as social relations. "The internalization in our experience of the external conversation of gestures that we carry on with other individuals in the social process is the essence of thinking" (Mead, 1934: 47).

At the end of the 19th century, the word 'consciousness', ennobled by Hegel and by German idealism, underwent a series of concentric attacks arising from the most diverse directions. From Nietzsche – who took consciousness to be a 'surface effect', and, even more radically, "our most miserable organ" (Nietzsche, 1967: Ch. III), "a long-term mistake" (Nietzsche, 2001: § 11) – to Charles Sanders Peirce, who added to his list of "incapacities" the faculty of introspection (Peirce, 1992: Ch. 3), up to William James, who worked, as we have seen, in the direction of a demolition of the "non

entity called consciousness" (James, 1912: Ch. 1), and finally to Mead and Vygotskij. The list should not go too far, especially in the field of philosophy. Supporters of consciousness will have still many cards to play in its defense, and with excellent arguments. From Brentano to Husserl, from Jaspers to Sartre, consciousness will continue to exhibit its own primacy as a transcendental and foundational element of human knowledge and balance.

Yet, Mead's view deconstructs the traditional interpretation of the mind and of the open access to our thoughts, the reference to a common ground and the building of an internal, free space. These are decisive issues, especially in our present time, where the space between private and public seems to flake and lose its traditional borders. The effort to understand how this space originates and how it evolves remains an ineludible task for the future of philosophy.

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